

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	ZHY-1-26- IBN-5-1% RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	15	Acq. Method Set:	1%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	zhy 1 26
Injection Volume:	3.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	11/18/2022 16:16:04 CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 20:40:00 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	11.901	1338579	50.53	65555
2	13.488	1310330	49.47	58028

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-130-IBN-5-1% asy	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20221118
Vial:	15	Acq. Method Set:	1%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	lm 4 130
Injection Volume:	3.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	16.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	11/18/2022 17:40:43 CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 20:39:41 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	11.971	162933	4.16	9652
2	13.277	3752600	95.84	168154